

Kinetic Study of Oxidation of L-Sorbose by Thallic Perchlorate

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Manuscript received 13 July 1981, revised 8 March 1982, accepted 10 December 1982

The oxidation of L-sorbose by thallic perchlorate has a first order dependence on $Tl(III)$ concentration. Variation of rate with L-sorbose is consistent with Michaelis-Menten kinetics. The rate is retarded by acidity, chloride and acetate ions. The thermodynamic parameters are reported. Suitable steps are proposed and rate law is given to explain the results obtained.

THALLIUM(III) is a fairly moderate oxidant which has been little exploited until recently. Kinetic studies, a few in number, make use of its perchlorate, acetate and chloride which can be prepared directly from thallium(III) oxide or hydroxide. Earlier, we reported the kinetics of oxidation of L-sorbose by vanadium(V)¹. We are now reporting the same with thallic perchlorate.

Experimental

The oxidant solution of thallic perchlorate was prepared by dissolving thallium(III) oxide (B.D.H. AnalaR) in 70% perchloric acid (Reidel) and standardised iodometrically. L-Sorbose solution was prepared fresh each day in double distilled water. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR/BDH grade.

The reaction was initiated by adding thallium(III) perchlorate solution to the reaction mixture containing L-sorbose, perchloric acid etc. both the solutions being equilibrated at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The rate of reaction was followed by determining thallium(III) concentration iodometrically. In most of the cases the duplicate rate measurements were reproducible to $\sim 5\%$.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics :

Pseudo first order rate constant, k_{obs} , at low $Tl(III)$ concentrations was calculated from the integrated form of the equation (1).

$$-\frac{d[Tl(III)]}{dt} = k_{obs} [Tl(III)] \quad \dots (1)$$

The oxidation rate increased with L-sorbose concentration and decreased with $HClO_4$ concentrations (Table 1). A linear plot of $1/[L\text{-sorbose}]$ versus $1/k_{obs}$ can be obtained with a positive intercept indicating that the order with respect to L-sorbose varies as $[L\text{-sorbose}]/a + [L\text{-sorbose}]$. The

dependence of rate on $[L\text{-sorbose}]$ is consistent with Michaelis-Menten kinetics, showing an evidence of complex formation before the rate determining step.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF $[L\text{-SORBOSE}]$ AND $[HClO_4]$ ON RATE AT 65° AND $[Tl(III)] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

$[L\text{-sorbose}]$ $\times 10^4 M$	$[HClO_4]$ M	$k_{obs} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
1.0	1.00	2.98
2.0	1.00	3.24
3.0	1.00	4.72
4.0	1.00	6.18
5.0	1.00	7.93
2.0	0.75	3.40
2.0	0.50	3.75
2.0	0.25	4.24
2.0	0.17	4.88

The observed decrease in rate with acidity (Table 1) is further confirmed when similar results are observed at constant $[ClO_4^-]$ maintained with $NaClO_4$ (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[H^+]$ ON RATE AT 65° AND CONSTANT $[ClO_4^-] = 1.0 M$

$[H^+]$ M	H_0	$k_{obs} \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$
0.17	+0.25	3.87
0.25	+0.20	2.95
0.50	+0.01	2.78
0.75	-0.16	2.68
1.00	-0.34	2.55

In most of the other oxidation reactions involving metal ion oxidants, the converse effect of $[H^+]$ on rate is observed.

$\log k_{obs}$ has been plotted against H_0 and the slope value has been computed as 0.80. ω value (4.40) and ϕ value (2.44) have been obtained from the Bunnett² and Bunnett-Olsen⁴ plots.

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The oxidation rate is strongly inhibited by chloride and acetate ions (Table 3).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [Cl⁻] AND [CH₃COO⁻] ON RATE

[Ti(III)] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M [HClO ₄] = 0.17 M		[L-sorbose] = 2.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M Temp. = 65°	
[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³ M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	[CH ₃ COO ⁻] × 10 ³ M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹
0.00	4.38	0.00	4.38
1.60	1.97	2.88	0.80
3.00	0.92	5.76	0.59
5.00	0.28	9.64	0.43
6.00	0.09	11.50	0.40

Further, the rate has been found influenced when ionic strength is varied by the addition of NaClO₄ (Table 4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON RATE

[Ti(III)] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M [HClO ₄] = 1.0 M		[L-sorbose] = 2.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M Temp. = 65°	
[NaClO ₄] M	[μ] M	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
0.00	1.01	3.24	
0.25	1.26	4.93	
0.50	1.51	5.90	
1.00	2.01	6.37	
1.50	2.51	7.49	

From the effect of temperature on reaction rate the activation parameters ΔH[‡] and ΔS[‡] have been calculated as 25.29 ± 0.05 kcal mole and 2.27 ± 0.03 e.u., respectively (Table 5). The former is obtained from the slope and the latter from the intercept of a plot of log k_{obs}/T against 1/T.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON RATE

[Ti(III)] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M [HClO ₄] = 1.0 M		[L-sorbose] = 2.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M	
Temp. K	10 ³ /T	k _{obs} × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
328	3.05	0.84	
333	3.00	1.24	
338	2.96	3.24	
343	2.92	4.58	
348	2.87	7.95	

Stoichiometry :

It is found that one mole of L-sorbose is oxidised to formaldehyde and formic acid by ~ 5 equivalents of oxidant. The stoichiometric equation therefore can be represented as :

The products have been confirmed by the usual tests and by spot test⁸.

Ti(III) in aqueous perchloric acid medium exists as Ti³⁺ and its hydrolysed forms as Ti(OH)²⁺

and Ti(OH)₂⁺. In the present reaction the [H⁺] dependence (Table 2) can be explained by assuming Ti(OH)²⁺ as the reactive species⁶⁻⁹. The formation of Ti(OH)₂⁺ can be neglected as the second hydrolysis constant of Ti³⁺ is very small.

The kinetics data obtained can now be accounted for by the following proposed steps (3-5) and the rate law derived (6).

$$-\frac{d[Ti(III)]}{dt} = \frac{k K K_h [Ti(III)] [L\text{-sorbose}] [H^+]^{-1}}{1 + K_h [H^+]^{-1} + K K_h [H^+]^{-1} [L\text{-sorbose}]} \dots (6)$$

From (1) and (6) it follows that

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k K K_h [L\text{-sorbose}] [H^+]^{-1}}{1 + K_h [H^+]^{-1} + K K_h [H^+]^{-1} [L\text{-sorbose}]} \dots (7)$$

Equation (7) explains the Michaelis-Menten kinetics in case of substrate variation (Table 1) and inverse dependence on [H⁺] (Table 2).

The value of K_h has been computed for the present experimental condition (temp. 65°) from the reported value of K_h^{10,11} and that of enthalpy of hydrolysis¹² in the literature. It was then used in calculating the formation constant of complex (K) and its rate of disproportion as 0.80 mole⁻¹ and 32.25 × 10⁻⁴ sec⁻¹, respectively from the Michaelis and Menten plot.

The retardation of rate due to chloride and acetate ions (Table 3) is due to the formation of strong covalent complex with Ti³⁺ which blocks the coordination sites on Ti³⁺ and thereby inhibit the formation of intermediate complex⁹.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely thank Prof. R. P. Bhatnagar, Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior for encouragement and U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of Junior Research Fellowship to (S. K. S.).

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FADNIS & SHRIVASTAVA : KINSTIC STUDY OF OXIDATION OF L-SORBOSE BY THALLIC-PERCHLORATE

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